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Contents

1 Introduction.....	2
2. Manufacture of reflective X-ray optics.....	3
3. Metrology methods and devices for the inspection of X-ray mirrors.....	4
3.1 Interferometric devices	4
3.2 Optical Deflectometers	6
3.3 Calibration	7
3.4 Metrology and shape optimization	7
3.5 Metrology data handling.....	8
4 Conclusion and outlook.....	9
5. References.....	10
6. Appendix.....	12

Report on performance of candidate metrology techniques supporting manufacturing process of freeform optics

1 Introduction

Highly precise and reliable metrology methods are essential to enable the manufacture and quality verification of ultra-precise X-ray-optical systems required by accelerator-based photon sources. For X-ray mirror optics (which for the purposes of this document also includes the closely related substrates required for reflective diffraction grating and multilayer manufacture) accurate metrology data are an essential input to iterative correction of the figure errors of the optical surface. . Driven by improvements in the quality of X-ray light-sources, requirements upon X-ray mirror surface quality are increasingly of sub-nm figure precision. To approach these specifications, X-ray mirror manufacturing increasingly involves the use ‘deterministic figuring’ methods. Conventional ‘full-aperture’ polishing processes restrict the figure of mirrors to simple geometries¹ with high symmetry (flat, spherical, cylindrical, toroidal). The application of figuring methods with tool sizes smaller than the clear aperture of the optic has opened the path towards the manufacture of optics with lower symmetry such as elliptical & hyperbolic cylinders, ellipsoidal and even free-form optics. In these instances, one of the major challenges for the manufacturing process is to provide surface metrology of sufficient precision.

¹ Excluding the particular case of stress-polishing [1]

The manufacture of X-ray mirrors for accelerator-based light sources requires precise metrology to guide the figuring and polishing process and means that high performance metrology devices are required at the manufacturing facilities. Most of the light sources need similar systems for quality control and offline performance evaluation once the optics are integrated into the optomechanical systems. This report presents the necessary characteristics for metrology processes for X-ray mirrors with particular emphasis upon the requirements for supporting the manufacturing process of flat, curved and free-form mirrors. It then attempts to give an overview of the characteristics of different metrology systems and methods. Finally, it attempts to provide a guide of good experimental practice for the surface metrology aiming for sub-nm precision surfaces both in terms of data collection and analysis. The subject of this report is an analysis of the different metrology methods and systems regarding their capability to characterize the WP3-developed substrate quality, as well as for curved mirror substrates in future.

2. Manufacture of reflective X-ray optics

Due to a combination of highly favourable mechanical and thermal properties, as well as its availability in large dimensions, the majority of X-ray mirrors for accelerator-based light sources are manufactured from single crystal silicon. The raw material is typically in the form of ingots of the type used for the manufacturer of semi-conducting wafers for microelectronics fabrication. After rough machining (by sawing, milling and grinding) of the ingot to the required format, the optical surface of the silicon blank is polished.

In almost all instances initial polishing is performed by abrasive material removal. These methods can be applied over the full aperture if the required polished surface figure is flat, spherical or toroidal. Whilst these full-aperture methods can in some instances achieve remarkably high quality surfaces, with slope errors and height errors respectively in the $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{rad rms}$ and $\sim 5 \text{ nm rms}$ range, the convergence of the polishing process can be unpredictable and lead to poor part yields or extensive part rework. This impact on yield and the added cost of reworking means that such traditional polishing approaches can be uneconomic for the routine production of optics satisfying the increasingly stringent demands of modern accelerator-based X-ray light sources. The use of deterministic figuring methods, where polishing is performed with a polishing/figuring tool smaller than the clear aperture, can target the localization of material removal (or addition) within small areas of the optical aperture. This approach allows a faster and predictable manufacturing cycle with significant gains in productivity. Such methods also extend the polishing process to the manufacture of lower symmetry surface figures (e.g. ellipsoidal, parabolic or elliptical cylinders, freeform²) and in some instances allow further improvement of the optical surface quality. Deterministic figuring methods can use abrasive or chemo-mechanical polishing – ‘computer-controlled polishing’ but alternative approaches such as ion beam figuring, elastic emission machining and magnetorheological finishing are also regularly applied. Using these approaches, the amount of

² ISO standard 17450-1:2011: Optical surfaces with no translational or rotational symmetry about axes normal to the mean plane.

material removed in the figuring/polishing process can be locally varied down to lateral dimensions commensurate with the tool size. This may be achieved by varying the material removal rate, or more commonly the dwell time as a function tool position at the optical surface.

Usually the deterministic correction processes are implemented in several cycles to achieve the final target surface quality and the effectiveness of the iterative process relies on the availability of spatially resolved surface metrology with sufficient accuracy.

The manufacture of freeform surfaces is of increasing interest, for example, to compensate for gravity driven deformations of the optics when placed in its final attitude.

3. Metrology methods and devices for the inspection of X-ray mirrors

As X-ray mirrors are highly-fragile the use of tactile characterization methods such as stylus profilers risk damage of the super-polished optical aperture or the very delicate reflective coatings deposited on the mirror surfaces. Consequently the usual inspection tools are based upon optical sensing and non-contact methods. Due to the properties of X-ray reflection, X-ray mirrors are operated in grazing incidence configurations and therefore have highly asymmetric apertures. Moreover the diversity of optical geometries implemented at synchrotron and FEL light sources means that the size, surface figure and specifications of mirrors are specific to each application and that it is rare for a particular design to be manufactured in more than a few (< 5) units and more commonly mirrors are ordered in a single example. As a consequence of this large diversity in mirror format and small quantities any metrology methods must be highly versatile and cannot be optimized for a specific mirror design. As detailed in the milestone report MS13 (Superflat: Needs identification and assessment), to characterize the optical specifications with the required precision, the metrology methods should be capable of measuring:

- figure errors < 1nm rms (spatial frequencies in range $1/L - 1 \text{ mm}^{-1}$) where L is the dimension of the useful optical aperture in mm
- slope errors < 50 nrad rms (spatial frequencies in range $1/L - 1 \text{ mm}^{-1}$)
- roughness < 0.1 nm (spatial frequencies in range $1 - 1000 \text{ mm}^{-1}$)

across optical figures ranging from flat (radius > 200 km) to aspheric/ freeform surfaces with radius as low as 10 m. The sizes of the useful optical aperture, L can range from $\sim 50 \text{ mm}$ to $\sim 1000 \text{ mm}$.

3.1 Interferometric devices

Interferometric measurement devices are routinely used at optics manufacturers and in science to measure the quality of mirrors and other super-polished optical components. Interferometers of different designs and principles are commercially available from several vendors. Other instruments are available, but these often require expert users and in-house developments. As such, their use is typically limited to dedicated communities. Interferometers are the most common optical metrology instruments within optics industry.

Imaging interferometers, such as the Fizeau- or Twyman-Green type e.g. [2], can allow a fast and reliable measurement of the surface figure errors of an optical element. They can measure large mirrors using large aperture systems or sub-aperture stitching techniques. Interferometry is the method of choice for quality control in case of serial production of optics for visible light applications. In the case of curved spherical- or aspherical-optics, dedicated reference optics or computer-generated holograms (CGH) may be used. The characterization and subsequent compensation of the systematic errors introduced by the reference surfaces of such interferometers (the amplitudes of which are generally much greater than the target specifications) is a major challenge for the metrology of X-ray optics. In part due to the sensitivity of the measurements to such errors, the use of phase-scanning Fizeau interferometry has become the technique of choice for the measurement of the 2D surface figure. Extremely high performance has been achieved for mirrors for high-numerical aperture-EUV-lithography systems with parabolic shape. Similar to X-ray optics these mirrors require an ultimate polish and finishing at the atomic level of precision. Metrology systems to measure such mirrors are located in a $5 \times 10 \text{m}^2$ vacuum vessel and have a weight of 150t, see Reference [3]. Such metrology systems measuring EUV-optics can be optimized for small series production but the required budget to develop and operate similar instruments for ad-hoc X-ray mirror designs is beyond the capabilities of our labs and most commercial vendors.

As indicated earlier the beam-shaping mirrors in synchrotron- and FEL-science are each unique in their dimensions and figure. Whilst, with careful determination of the systematic errors, plane mirrors can be readily measured by means of interferometry, curved mirrors require some additional equipment and experience due, for example, to the manifestation of so-called 'retrace-errors' when the systems are not used to measure in a common path configuration e.g. [4,5]. However, with appropriate precautions phase-scanning Fizeau interferometry can also be applied to measure high-quality curved mirrors with the necessary precision.

The spatial resolution of Fizeau interferometers is determined primarily by a combination of the image field size and the sensor (usually a CMOS camera) dimensions. Whilst the full length of large aperture X-ray mirrors may be measured using interferometers with a large reference surface or by measuring the mirror in oblique incidence e.g. [6] the attainable spatial resolution may be insufficient to cover the specified spatial frequency range. As a consequence the tendency is to perform the measurement of large aperture optics using sub-aperture stitching measurements. Such stitching approaches have been routinely used for the characterization of the flat samples produced in phase 2 of the WP3 Superflat PCP [7]. Sub-aperture stitching techniques are however subject to introducing other (primarily low spatial frequency) errors into the surface measurements which can be partially mitigated by the introduction of complementary measurement systems and careful data acquisition and processing protocols [8].

Interference microscopes (with Michelson or Mirau objectives) [9] are commonly used to measure the micro-roughness of optical elements. Such instruments are standard at most vendors and at science facilities. Furthermore, they can perform micro-stitching interferometry to measure large aperture sections with very high spatial resolution. Micro-stitching is used at only a few commercial vendors

world-wide (e.g. JTEC in Japan), as well as at specialized research facilities (Osaka Univ., ESRF, Diamond, and other synchrotron labs) see also at [10].

Combining stitching interferometry and micro-stitching interferometry allows the measurement and the manufacture of mirrors with sub-nm precision across an extended spatial frequency range, as demonstrated by JTEC-company and Osaka University in Japan [11].

With appropriate instruments imaging interferometric methods allow characterization of mirrors with high spatial resolution. Measurement data are used to provide feedback for deterministic surface finishing technology like Ion Beam Figuring (IBF), elastic emission machining (EEM), computer aided polishing (CAP) or magnetorheological finishing (MRF).

Table 1 in the Annex gives an overview on the different metrology methods and devices currently in use (or under development) to characterize ultra-precise mirrors for synchrotron- or FEL facilities.

3.2 Optical Deflectometers

The optical deflectometer is a common and well-established instrument at synchrotron and FEL-facilities. Since the late 1980s, the Long Trace Profiler (LTP) [12] became the most used instrument to measure long synchrotron mirrors up to 1.5m in length. The LTP allows a direct measurement of the slope and slope error (deviation relative to the required profile) along a single line of plane or curved mirrors. In many cases, this is sufficient for the verification of mirror slope/shape error and curvature. As the irradiated aperture of most synchrotron mirrors is only a few millimeters in width, a line-scan (or a few lines) is often sufficient for performance evaluation. The use of LTP-line-scan data for deterministic surface finishing has never been established in Industry. A further slope-measuring profiler is the Nanometer Optic component measuring Machine (NOM) [13]. The NOM was developed at BESSY (today a part of HZB). NOM-systems are now commonly use at many synchrotron labs in Europe (HZB, Diamond, and ALBA) as well as in the US, Asia, and South America. Like the LTP, the NOM allows single line-scan measurements with high precision and repeatability. The BESSY-NOM allows a 2D-slope-mapping of plane and cylinder-like or mild spherical mirrors. These data have been provided to manufacturers to enable deterministic surface finishing [14]. In general NOM-2D-surface mapping is a time-consuming process, thus it has never been established at the manufacturer side. Slope-measuring profilers are expert-user systems since their handling and calibration take special care. A further direct slope-measuring method is the Extended Shear Angle Device (ESAD) [15]. ESAD is a development of the Physikalisch Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) in Germany. It is certified as a national reference for flatness in Germany, but allows only the measurement of plane surfaces. ESAD allows a calibration of reference-flats for interferometry, as well as a cross-check for slope-measuring profilers. This has been realized to the BESSY-NOM, and it is offered as service by the PTB to industry too.

In general, the line profile data provided by LTP, NOM and ESAD devices is non-ideal for guiding any deterministic figure correction process. They can however provide very high quality data on long mirrors without the risk of stitching artefacts which can degrade the low spatial frequency height

evaluation by interferometric methods. For the highest angular sensitivity the LTP and NOM instruments have a maximum spatial frequency of $\sim 0.25\text{-}0.5\text{ mm}^{-1}$. In the LEAPS facilities, such systems are often implemented in parallel with interferometric methods where the redundancy and complementarity of different instruments can act as an 'alarm' in the case of instrument malfunction.

Moreover, when compared with interferometric methods, due to the relative rapidity of the measurement process, such instruments can be very powerful for the evaluation and calibration of mechanical bender systems which are widely used for dynamic tuning of the mirror bending radius.

There are two further new instruments to be noted here, the SHARPeR and the Speckle Angle Metrology method (SAM). Both methods measure the deflection of a visible light probe beam by the X-ray mirror. .

SHARPeR is a development by Imagine Optics, in cooperation with Soleil, NSLS-II and ESRF based upon the use of Shack-Hartmann sensing [16] It employs sub-aperture stitching methods to recover directly the 2D slope profile of the measured surface.. SAM [17] is a promising technology under development at Diamond Light Source which uses advanced image analysis algorithms to recover the local slope from laser speckle images which are distorted/translated during reflection by the slope variations of the imperfect test optic.

Both SHARPeR and SAM can give a 2D slope profiles of the test surface. Neither system has yet demonstrated better performance than the Fizeau interferometric methods in practical applications and can be considered as expert systems under development.

3.3 Calibration

The calibration of metrology devices is an essential step towards improving the accuracy of such instruments. It makes them traceable to a well-known reference standard e.g. by national metrology institutes. This makes such instruments highly comparable and reliable within the community. Beside the characterization and calibration of references (like reference flats as well as spheres and CGH's) at certified facilities there have been several methods developed over time to calibrate interferometers. A common method of self-calibration is the so-called three-flat tests, which is applied at many labs [18]. Slope measuring profilers can be calibrated versus angle references generated by the angle comparator at the PTB [19]. Several labs have established in-house devices and methods to calibrate such instruments, including the vertical angle comparator (VAC) [20] at HZB, and the NANGO-system at Diamond [21]. The systematic errors of NOM and LTP systems may be evaluated and compensated by the use of special acquisition methods generating highly redundant data sets [22] but the application of such methods tends to be limited to optics with significant curvature.

3.4 Metrology and shape optimization

Today's state-of-the-art mirrors are generally polished and finished by means of deterministic technology. Only pre-polishing is realized by classical pitch-polishing with a diamond slurry and chemo-mechanical polishing, as is used for wafer polishing in the semiconductor industry. Based on metrology data, the residual shape error of the optical surface can be calculated and stored in a data file. This

enables a local shape-correction and improvement of the mirror's aperture by means of a spatially resolved polishing system. The quality of the metrology data is essential for the final state of the mirror. In a worst case, different type of systematic error contribution caused by the metrology device can be machined into the aperture shape. A large part of systematic error contributions can be overcome by careful calibration or error-suppression techniques. This is common technology used at most optics vendors today. Only 2D-data are suitable to guide the surface correction process, as single line-scan data can't be used for such applications. The spatial resolution of the measuring system matters for such tasks. This is a clear advantage of all the interferometric instruments compared to line-scan data collected by profilometry. To limit the impact of unknown systematic measurement errors, the combination of data from two or more measuring devices allows a cross-check to eliminate errors.

3.5 Metrology data handling

Commercially available instruments like Fizeau interferometer or micro-interferometers are sold as complete systems, including computer and software to operate the system and analyze data. Nevertheless their integration in a measurement process adapted to the evaluation of surface errors of X-ray mirrors usually requires both specific hardware to allow the implementation of sub-aperture stitching methods and adapted data processing algorithms. Open-source code like GWYDDION [23] or PyLOSt [24,25] is available for advanced data analysis. GWYDDION is a development by the Department of Nanometrology, of the Czech National Metrology Institute (CMI) and is supported by a large user and developer community. It has seen several updates over the last decade. PyLOSt was developed especially to handle the data needs of X-ray optical elements such as mirrors or grating blanks and in particular provide well documented algorithms for the processing and stitching of sub-apertures to provide reliable maps of height errors. During the WP3 Superflat activities, PyLOSt has been adopted by some of the European X-ray optics manufacturers for these stitching capabilities. The manufacturers typically develop their own data handling algorithms to transform the height error measurements to guide their polishing and finishing systems.

It is however advisable to promote common methods for analysing and correcting metrology data. Specific software tools for metrology data analysis have been developed by the LEAPS consortium, during the Superflat project, for the sake of inter-comparison between different metrology instruments from various laboratories. They can be freely downloaded from the [Superflat-scripts repository](#) [26]. They provide standardised methods for evaluating the frequency distribution of surface figure errors. When several sources of data are available, such as full-field and stitching data, they may help to discriminate the frequency range in which each source is faithful and reliable for local finishing. Following internal discussions and with industrials these tools will be extended to combine together such data with different frequency content.

In this context, the Superflat consortium has also defined a basic interchange file structure for surface metrology data [27] which includes important metadata. Conversion from usual commercial format to this standard is also included in the Superflat scripts.

4 Conclusion and outlook

Ultra-precise metrology devices are key in enabling the inspection and manufacturing of high-end X-ray mirrors with single- or sub-nm-precision. Interferometry is the most common method used by Vendors. It has been traditionally used by the optics community over the past few decades, and is well known and supported by a large world-wide community of experts at companies, universities, and other research facilities. Interferometric methods allow the inspection of optics with high spatial resolution (see also the Table in the Appendix). Data handling is well established. Many commercially available IBF-systems are prepared to be operated based on such data. This is especially the case for plane mirrors and curved mirrors, if the latter is a subject of serial production and a dedicated reference is available, see also Ref. [1]. It is different for single-piece production, as is required for most cases of beam shaping X-ray mirrors for synchrotrons or FEL's. In such cases, stitching methods or the combination of interferometry and alternative methods have been applied with much success.

The acquired experience of X-ray manufacturers in using both Fizeau- and micro-interferometers is a considerable advantage when incorporating such devices into appropriate instrumentation or processes for performing stitching measurements. These systems currently offer the most flexible and rapid metrology for evaluation of most optical figures (including freeform optics) at accuracy levels compatible with the mirror specifications currently required by X-ray light sources. During the WP3 activities the project team has worked closely with European optics manufacturers to assist them in improving and validating their metrology processes based on interferometric methods.

Slope measuring profilers like the LTP or NOM are well established for measuring shape and figure errors of plane and curved optics including cylinders, ellipses, toroids and spheres. As they usually provide line-scan data only, and their spatial resolution is limited to about 2 mm, their data have limitations of use for deterministic surface finishing. However, since these instruments have a large flexibility in measuring different type of curved shape and can be precisely calibrated, their use is an important option for the final acceptance measurement of X-ray mirrors.

New methods, such as the SHARPeR system or SAM, have shown great potential to characterize X-ray mirrors. However, further work is required to calibrate such systems and bring them into routine operation. In the current state, they can be indicated as expert systems under development.

Considerable progress has been made in developing metrology tools capable of providing the 2D correction data for flat, spherical and elliptical cylinder optics at the sub-nm and sub-50 nrad scale. Nevertheless, the measurement the full surface errors of toroidal or cylindrical surfaces with large asymmetry of the radius of curvature (e.g. with tangential radius \sim m or km and sagittal radius \sim mm or cm) remains to be resolved. This is beyond the scope of the WP3 work program but there is the prospect of extending interferometric methods to achieve the necessary surface height accuracy for improving the manufacturing quality of such optics. This will be a future potential development activity benefiting both optics manufacturers and X-ray light-source users.

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6. Appendix

Table 1, On the performance of different methods of metrology for the inspection and characterization of SR-mirror substrates

Method	Principle	Spatial resolution	Pros	Cons	System can be calibrated	Usable at SR-lab/Industry	Additional comments
Fiizeau single-pass interferometry	Interferometry	Depends on pixel size of CCD and zoom factor, but ~ 35 μm (with zoom) to 50 μm (without zoom)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to use / align • High spatial resolution • Fast • Provides 2D maps • Less sensitive to environment compared to other methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited by quality of reference flat (for Rc evaluation) • Limits in size of optic that can be measured (aperture of Fizeau) 	Yes	Yes / Yes	Used by most vendors of X-ray mirrors
Fiizeau double-pass interferometry	Interferometry	Depends on pixel size of CCD and zoom factor and angle of inclination, but < 1 mm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can measure long mirrors • Provides 2D maps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More complicated to align than single-pass • Limited by quality of reference flat and reflector flat. • More complicated / numerous systematic errors 	Yes	Yes / Yes	Not useful for < 100 nrad mirrors?
Stitching Fizeau interferometry	Interferometry	Similar to single-pass Fizeau	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can measure long mirrors • Provides higher quality results than single-pass Fizeau • Provides 2D maps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stitching hardware needed • Stitching algorithms needed (can use PyLOST) 	Yes	Yes / Yes	Used by JTEC & TSESO, +?
Stitching micro-interferometry	Interferometry	Depends on objective magnification, typically a few μm at 2.5X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highest spatial resolution • Provides 2D maps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stitching algorithms needed (can use PyLOST) • 2d Limited in sagittal direction • Limitations to measure large optics • Uncertainties for spatial periods >100mm for flat mirror • Slow measurements 	Yes	Yes / Yes	Used by JTEC, but no other vendors?

Method	Principle	Spatial resolution	Pros	Cons	System can be calibrated	Usable at SR-lab/Industry	Additional comments
Sharper	wavefront sensing	1.2 mm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can measure long mirrors 2D slope maps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slow measurements Sensitive to environment Low spatial resolution 2d Limited in sagittal direction to sensor size (without x-y stitching implementation) 	Yes	Yes / no?	Expert system
LTP/NOM	angular deflection	1.0 to 2.0 mm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can measure long mirrors Excellent repeatability Can measure curved surfaces 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low spatial resolution, Can be slow measurements (but depends on instrument and scan type) 1D line profiles for most instruments 2D area scans are time consuming 	Yes	Yes / Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expert system NOM is used by Crystal Scientific, but not calibrated or optimised
SAM*	angular deflection	Sub-mm to few mm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can measure long mirrors Can produce 2D information map Can measure curved mirrors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Computation speed is low Currently a research instrument 	Yes	Yes / no?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expert system Can be used to characterize strongly curved optics

* Speckle Angle Metrology (SAM) at Diamond: Wang et al. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41377-021-00632-4>

